

SUSPENDING MUSEUM OBJECTS

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Why do we do it?

- ▣ Dramatic effect
- ▣ Save space
- ▣ Help tell a story
- ▣ Just because we like it
- ▣ Or how about as bait to tempt visitors in to the store

V3388

G-ALFU

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LONDON

NO. 1

What do we suspend?

Do we choose an object that:

- ▣ Has little history ?
- ▣ Is core to the story we are telling ?
- ▣ Is common ?
- ▣ To keep it out of harms way ?
- ▣ Or just because it fits ?

Who decides?

- ▣ The display designer ?
- ▣ The Director ?
- ▣ The curator ?
- ▣ The conservator ?
- ▣ The engineer ?
- ▣ The educator ?
- ▣ All the above ?

What do we need to know?

- ▣ Is the building capable of taking the weight ?
- ▣ Will it fit ?
- ▣ Is the object structurally sound ?
- ▣ Who is responsible for each stage ?

Structural engineer

Object engineer

Design engineer

One approach to suspending an object

- ▣ Suspension system designer
- ▣ Suspension fittings manufacturer
- ▣ Suspension fittings installation
- ▣ Lifting specialist

System design engineer

- ▣ Design the complete suspension system
- ▣ Liaise with structural engineer
- ▣ Liaise with display designer
- ▣ Supply certified manufacturing drawings
- ▣ Supply copies of all stress and design calculations
- ▣ Supply post suspension inspection requirement report

VIEW LOOKING AFT ON STARBOARD WING
PORT SIDE CPP HAND

AEROFOIL CROSS SECTION (UPPER WING / MID-PLANE JOINT)

AEROFOIL PROFILE (UPPER WING / MID-PLANE JOINT)

EXISTING WING / MID-PLANE JOINT

FORWARD LIFTING ATTACHMENT

M/C CONNECTION - UPPER WING / MID-PLANE ATTACHMENT

(51C KG SML)

SCALE 1:1

COMPUTER PRODUCED DRAWING
USING ...
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NO. 10100	REV. 1	DATE	1:20
DESIGNED BY	3 HUNLEY	APPROVED BY	A. HAYSTON
DRWING NO.	3 HUNLEY	SCALE	1:20
TITLE	LWM DUXFORD RAF FGS SUPPORT SCHEME	INDICATED IN SECTION	CD 3 AU
PE629-2273-ASY			

B. TERNT 10M

155 D - ...
155 E - ...
155 F - ...
155 G - ...
155 H - ...
155 I - ...
155 J - ...
155 K - ...
155 L - ...
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155 V - ...
155 W - ...
155 X - ...
155 Y - ...
155 Z - ...

155 C - RA. ADDED TO SHT 1
AS REF
08/19/85 07/15/04

155 D - 155H 10 X 20
ADDED - SEE SHT 2

155 E - TRUE DIM 155S
WAS FINE DIM 155S, SHT 1
JAT/INIS 05/06/05

155 F - PART NUMBER OF
ITEM 17 ON SCHEM
MOD PD
TO - 51C W/S - 157
JAT/INIS 07/06/05

ALL DIMENSIONS IN MILLIMETRES UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED
DIMENSIONS TO BE SHOWN AS DIMENSIONS UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED
DIMENSIONS TO BE SHOWN AS DIMENSIONS UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED

Suspension system fitting manufacture

- ▣ Who manufactures and certifies the fittings to drawing ?

Fitting installation

- ▣ Who installs the fittings ?
- ▣ Who verifies the installation ?
- ▣ Who accepts responsibility ?

Lifting the object in to position

- ▣ Who lifts the object in to it's display position ?
- ▣ What are their responsibilities ?

What happens after suspension?

- ▣ Can you reach your object to clean it ?
- ▣ Can you reach your object to inspect the system and the object ?
- ▣ Do you record your inspection findings ?
- ▣ Do you have a plan in place to deal with any problems you may encounter ?
- ▣ Can you get your object down ?
- ▣ Can you still move other objects beneath it on the floor ?

Exit

What happens if you can not suspend?

- ▣ You can mount on a pole
- ▣ You can raise on supports
- ▣ You can partial suspend

SR-71A "Blackbird"

463209

S WZ

Please use the main entrance
at the other side of the building
This is an emergency exit only

Entrance

463209

WZ-S

